

Research paper

Dizocilpine derivatives as neuroprotective NMDA receptor antagonists without psychomimetic side effects

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ABSTRACT

We aimed to prepare novel dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen derivatives that act on *N*-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptors with potential neuroprotective effects. Our approach involved modifying the tropane moiety of MK-801, a potent open-channel blocker known for its psychomimetic side effects, by introducing a seven-membered ring with substituted base moieties specifically to alleviate these undesirable effects. Our *in silico* analyses showed that these derivatives should have high gastrointestinal absorption and cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB). Our pharmacokinetic studies in rats supported this conclusion and confirmed the ability of leading compounds **3i** and **6f** to penetrate the BBB. Electrophysiological experiments showed that all compounds exhibited different inhibitory activity towards the two major NMDA receptor subtypes, GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B. Of the selected compounds intentionally differing in the inhibitory efficacy, **6f** showed high relative inhibition (~90 % for GluN1/GluN2A), while **3i** showed moderate inhibition (~50 %). An *in vivo* toxicity study determined that compounds **3i** and **6f** were safe at 10 mg/kg doses with no adverse effects. Behavioral studies demonstrated that these compounds did not induce hyperlocomotion or impair prepulse inhibition of startle response in rats. Neuroprotective assays using a model of NMDA-induced hippocampal neurodegeneration showed that compound **3i** at a concentration of 30 μM significantly reduced hippocampal damage in rats. These results suggest that these novel dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen derivatives are promising candidates for developing NMDA receptor-targeted therapies with minimal psychotomimetic side effects.

1. Introduction

N-methyl-D-aspartate (NMDA) receptors are essential ionotropic glutamate receptors facilitating excitatory synaptic transmission within the mammalian central nervous system (CNS). They are crucial for the pathology of several CNS disorders, including epilepsy, Alzheimer's

disease (AD), and autism [1]. In the adult forebrain, the prevalent forms of NMDA receptors are the diheteromeric GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B, along with the triheteromeric GluN1/GluN2A/GluN2B receptors [1,2]. The GluN subunits share a common structure: an extracellular N-terminal domain, a ligand-binding domain formed by S1 and S2 segments, a transmembrane domain (TMD), and an intracellular

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C-terminal domain. The TMD includes three transmembrane-spanning helices (M1, M3, and M4) and a membrane loop (M2), with the M2 loops and M3 helices together, forming the ion channel and the binding site for Mg^{2+} , which blocks the receptor in its resting state [1,3,4].

Numerous pharmacological compounds modulate NMDA receptors via competitive, allosteric, or open-channel blocking mechanisms, providing a broad range of options for developing targeted treatments for human disorders linked to NMDA receptor dysregulation, including Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease, epilepsy, pain, and depression [5–10]. Tricyclic compounds, including a medium-sized (six to eight-member) ring, often showed protection against NMDA-induced toxicity on neuronal cell lines as a part of their multifunctional profile (also serving as cholinesterase inhibitors), thus being potential candidates against neurodegenerative diseases [11–13]. Open-channel blockers, in particular, are noteworthy due to the approval of memantine for neurodegenerative conditions like AD [14,15], ketamine's use as an anesthetic, and the recent approval of (S)-ketamine as an antidepressant [16,17]. Recent structural data indicate that the binding sites for memantine, ketamine, and MK-801 (Fig. 1A) overlap within the central vestibule of the NMDAR ion channel, specifically between the channel gate and the selectivity filter. These molecules interact differently with various residues within this region. Such a difference in interaction may be crucial as it determines the pharmacological effects [18–20]. Both memantine and ketamine inhibit NMDA receptors in a voltage-dependent manner, with IC_{50} values in the micromolar range for GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptors at resting membrane potentials [21]. Moreover, onset and offset inhibitory kinetics are fast, ranging from milliseconds to seconds, depending on the concentration and subunit composition [22]. The fast kinetics is believed to be why both drugs are well tolerated in clinical use. In contrast, dizocilpine (MK-801) is known for its high affinity, showing IC_{50} values at resting potentials in the nanomolar range: 0.013–0.3 μM and 0.009–0.07 μM for GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptors, respectively [23–25], and near-'irreversible' binding within the ion channel pore (about 1.5 h at resting potentials [26]), leading to a strong psychomimetic effect [27,

28], which limits its clinical application [29,30]. The "irreversible" action of MK-801 is thought to result from strong hydrophobic interactions between its benzene rings and aromatic amino acid residues in the ion channel pore [18,31]. Therefore, the unique pharmacological properties of individual open-channel blockers, including selectivity for different NMDAR subtypes and the kinetics of inhibition, determine their clinical relevance. Most MK-801 analogs are synthesized with an open central ring to prevent irreversible binding and the associated psychotomimetic effects [32,33]. Recently, we developed an MK-801 derivative, N-cyclobutyl-5H-dibenzo [a,d] [7]annulen-5-amine (K2060), which, unlike ketamine or memantine, contains two aromatic rings surrounding a central cycloheptenyl moiety. K2060 exhibited IC_{50} values between 0.6 and 0.7 μM for GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptors at resting membrane potential, and although K2060 retains benzene rings, it exhibited slower kinetics than memantine and ketamine [34]. This property may be due to the cyclic alkyl group and exocyclic secondary amine moiety in K2060's structure, which effectively restrict the molecule's conformation without changing the original compound's chemical and physical properties [35].

Encouraged by our recent data with K2060, we have designed a series of 27 novel dibenzo [a,d] [7]annulen derivatives that demonstrate varying inhibitory activity toward the major NMDA receptor subtypes. Applying an *in vitro* selection process of electrophysiology, cytotoxicity, and *in vivo* pharmacokinetics, the selected compounds were analyzed for *in vivo* side effects and neuroprotection assessment using an NMDA-induced hippocampal lesion.

2. Results and discussion

2.1. Design

The dibenzo [a,d] [7]annulen scaffold represents the core of the newly designed derivatives in this study. The compounds were structurally inspired by a previously published series of 9H-fluoren-9-amines [36] and unsubstituted 10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d] [7]

Fig. 1. A: Chemical structures of the known NMDA receptor antagonists. B: Design of novel dibenzo [a,d] [7]annulen derivatives possessing activity towards NMDA receptor.

annulen-5-amine showing the *anti*-NMDA receptor activity [37]. In this family, we combined scaffolds of the two well-known NMDA receptor ligands, tacrine, and carbazole, to obtain derivatives with micromolar potency toward the NMDA receptor [38–40]. Some of the presented derivatives have already been described before; for example, **3a**, **3b**, **3f**, **3n**, **6a**, **6b**, **6c**, **6h**, **6i**, and **6k** were patented in 1970 for treating epilepsy [41]. Derivatives **6a**, **6c**, **6e**, **6f**, **6k**, **6i**, and **6k** were patented by La Roche in the same year with potential psychostimulant effects against depression; however, without specification of the molecular target or receptor [42].

In this study, we designed a series of compounds based on known scaffolds of NMDA receptor antagonists, taking advantage of structural features from dizocilpine, phencyclidine (PCP), tacrine, and carbazole, thus aiming to explore their potential at the NMDA receptors. The main area of interest in the current series was to improve the affinity and potency of novel derivatives towards NMDA receptors. We specifically gained knowledge from discovering PCP derivatives. Introducing one or more methylene groups between two cyclic moieties resulted in ligand stiffening, which enhanced the affinity for NMDA receptors [43]. Consequently, we incorporated a seven-membered ring into the novel compounds, replacing the traditional five-membered ring. These molecules are structurally similar to MK-801 [44]. However, given its high affinity and slow clearance, MK-801 is associated with severe medicinal risks such as Olney's lesions and behavioral disturbance, thereby limiting its use in human medicine [29,30]. Therefore, to mitigate these risks, we altered the tropane moiety of MK-801, changed the ligand topology, and introduced substituted basic moieties (primary or secondary amines) at position 5 on the seven-membered ring (Fig. 1B).

2.2. *In silico* prediction of CNS and oral availability

In silico absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) testing provides a robust predictive framework for assessing peroral and CNS availabilities, which is crucial for targeting neurodegenerative diseases such as AD, where the CNS is the primary focus [45–47]. Additionally, peroral administration is preferred for dementia patients due to its convenience [48,49]. Thus, we initially screened the designed compounds *in silico* to predict their peroral and CNS availabilities and assessed potential pharmacokinetic profiles, drug-likeness, and ADME characteristics using the web-based tool SwissADME [50–52]. A prototype open-channel blocker of the NMDA receptor, memantine, was used as a reference compound with known CNS status and pharmacokinetic profile (Table 1; also in Tables S1 and S2, Supplementary Information) [53]. We also employed the blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeation score algorithm for CNS prediction, presuming CNS availability with the highest reported predictive score [54]. The results from the BBB score fit between 5 and 6 (except derivative 6k), indicating the high possibility for the compounds to permeate through the BBB [54]. Table S1 (Supplementary Information) presents the physiological parameters used for BBB score calculation. In general, most of the compounds also fulfill the drug-likeness in various pharmacological models defined by pharmaceutical companies like Veber's (GSK) [55], Lipinski's (Pfizer) [56], Egan's (Pharmacopeia) [57], Ghose's (Amgen) [58], and in some cases Muegge's (Bayer) [59] (results are presented in Table S2, Supplementary Information). In summary, the proposed derivatives showed a high probability of crossing the BBB with good predictive bioavailability and promising pharmacokinetic profile.

2.3. Chemistry

N-Substituted 10,11-dihydro-5*H*-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amines were prepared in one-step synthesis between the commercially available 5-chloro-10,11-dihydro-5*H*-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulene (1) with the various primary or secondary amines (**2a-o**) in dry acetonitrile (Scheme 1). This reaction afforded *N*-substituted-10,11-dihydro-5*H*-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amines (**3a-o**; Scheme 1) in mild-to-moderate yields

Table 1

Summary of *in silico* ADME and drug-likeness of derivatives **3a-o** and **6a-l** with memantine using various prediction models.

Compound	GIA ^a	BBB ^b	BBB score ^c	Lipinski ^d	Bio. Score ^e
3a	High	Yes	5.63	Yes	0.55
3b	High	Yes	5.63	Yes	0.55
3c	High	Yes	5.63	Yes	0.55
3d	High	Yes	5.62	Yes	0.55
3e	High	Yes	5.59	No	0.55
3f	High	Yes	5.59	No	0.55
3g	High	Yes	5.53	No	0.55
3h	High	Yes	5.10	No	0.55
3i	High	Yes	5.52	Yes	0.55
3j	High	Yes	5.68	Yes	0.55
3k	High	Yes	5.11	No	0.55
3l	High	Yes	5.48	Yes	0.55
3m	High	Yes	5.61	Yes	0.55
3n	High	Yes	5.14	No	0.55
3o	High	Yes	5.58	Yes	0.55
6a	High	Yes	5.33	Yes	0.55
6b	High	Yes	5.32	Yes	0.55
6c	High	Yes	5.31	Yes	0.55
6d	High	Yes	5.30	Yes	0.55
6e	High	Yes	5.29	Yes	0.55
6f	High	Yes	5.28	Yes	0.55
6g	High	Yes	5.23	No	0.55
6h	High	Yes	5.37	No	0.55
6i	High	Yes	5.17	Yes	0.55
6j	High	Yes	5.37	Yes	0.55
6k	High	Yes	4.82	Yes	0.55
6l	High	Yes	5.17	Yes	0.55
Memantine	High	Yes	4.61	Yes	0.55
Ketamine	High	Yes	5.29	Yes	0.55
MK-801	High	Yes	5.62	Yes	0.55

^a GIA = Gastrointestinal absorption.

^b BBB = Blood-brain barrier permeation.

^c ref. [54].

^d ref. [56].

^e Bio. Score = Bioavailability score [60].

(17–66 %). The compounds were converted to respective hydrochloride salts.

N-Substituted-5*H*-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amines (**6a-l**; Scheme 2) were prepared from the commercially available 5*H*-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-ol (4). Starting compound **4** was dissolved in dry DCM and treated with thionyl chloride to provide 5-chloro-5*H*-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulene (5), which was used directly for the next reaction (Scheme 2). Final derivatives **6a-l** were prepared as hydrochloride salts by the above procedure with moderate-to-good overall yields (41–74 %). The compounds **3a-o** and **6a-l** were characterized by ¹H, ¹³C NMR spectra, melting points, and HRMS analysis. LC analysis confirmed purity for all derivatives >95 % (Supplementary Information).

2.4. Evaluation of antagonist activity towards NMDA receptor, *in silico* analysis, and cytotoxicity

First, we determined the relative inhibition of all novel compounds on the two major dimeric NMDA receptor subtypes in the adult cortex – GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B [1] – using a clinically relevant concentration (3 μM). We kept the measured cells at a membrane potential of –60 mV, and the values of relative inhibition by the compounds were calculated from the L-glutamate-induced responses of human versions of the GluN1/GluN2A (hGluN1/hGluN2A) and GluN1/GluN2B (hGluN1/hGluN2B) receptors obtained under steady-state conditions. These experiments showed that all the studied compounds inhibit the responses of both NMDAR subtypes (see Table 2). Specifically, in the case of hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors, we obtained relative inhibition values ranging from ~5 % for compound **3h** to ~93 % for compound **6f**, while for hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors, we measured values ranging from ~3 % for compound **3i** to ~92 % for compound **6g**

Scheme 1. Synthetic procedure for preparing *N*-substituted-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amines **3a-o**. Reaction conditions: (i) MeCN, 40 °C, 3 h and (ii) HCl (37 % aq.sol.), MeOH, RT, 1 h.

Scheme 2. Synthetic procedure for preparing *N*-substituted-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amines **6a-l**. Reaction conditions: (i) SOCl₂, DCM, RT, 12 h; (ii) MeCN, 40 °C, 3 h and (iii) HCl (37 % aq.sol.), MeOH, RT, 1 h.

at a fixed dose of 3 μM of the tested compound. These results showed that our synthesized compounds contain potent inhibitors of both NMDAR subtypes. From a structure-activity point of view, derivatives **e**, **f**, and **g** in both the **3** and **6** series representing butylamine, *iso*-butylamine, and cyclohexylamine substituents, respectively, showed the most pronounced effect on both NMDAR subtypes. (see [Table 3](#))

The open-channel blockers of the NMDA receptors, such as ketamine and memantine, have been shown to have positive clinical effects in the treatment of depression and AD, but other open-channel blockers, such as MK-801, have significant negative side effects [1,29,30,61]. It can be assumed that the positive and negative effects of a given inhibitor of the NMDA receptor *in vivo* are caused by their affinity and the kinetics of inhibition, in addition to their availability in the CNS. Therefore, for further electrophysiological characterization and *in vivo* testing, we selected the **6f** compound, which showed >90 % (high) relative inhibition on both studied NMDA receptor subtypes, and the **3l** compound, which showed ~50 % (medium) relative inhibition values under the

same conditions. In further experiments, we generated concentration-response curves for **6f** (0.03–10 μM) and **3l** (0.3–300 μM) on both hGluN1/hGluN2A and hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors at negative (–60 mV) and positive (40 mV) membrane potentials ([Fig. 2A–D](#)). Our analysis showed that the **6f** compound exhibited IC₅₀ values ranging from ~0.2 to ~0.4 μM at negative membrane potential, whereas IC₅₀ values were approximately two orders of magnitude higher at positive membrane potential. Consistent with our data shown in [Table 2](#), we observed that the **3l** compound inhibited both NMDA receptor subtypes at negative membrane potential with IC₅₀ values of ~4 μM, while at positive membrane potential, IC₅₀ values were >200 μM (results summarized in [Table 3](#)). Comparing the IC₅₀ values obtained for memantine and ketamine, our measurements revealed that the compound **6f** exhibited a lower IC₅₀ value (at least at the hGluN1/hGluN2B receptor), while the **3l** compound had significantly higher IC₅₀ values (at both hGluN1/hGluN2A and hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors; [Table 3](#)). Our analysis demonstrated that the **6f** and **3l** compounds are

Table 2

Inhibitory effect of synthesized compounds at human GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptors expressed in the HEK293 cells and their cytotoxicity measured using CHO-K1 cells.

Compound	hGluN1/ hGluN2A RI ^a (%) ± SEM	hGluN1/ hGluN2B RI ^a (%) ± SEM	n (hGluN1/ hGluN2A/ hGluN1/ hGluN2B)	Cytotoxicity CHO-K1 IC ₅₀ ± SEM (μM)
3a	82.34 ± 3.25	70.97 ± 1.75	5/5	409.65 ± 4.85
3b	34.05 ± 4.60	51.84 ± 3.39	4/5	364.07 ± 25.58
3c	52.23 ± 5.23	76.92 ± 3.57	4/7	263.20 ± 11.30
3d	40.11 ± 3.42	53.57 ± 3.16	10/6	177.00 ± 6.60
3e	76.43 ± 4.03	85.79 ± 2.19	6/7	127.57 ± 7.55
3f	76.79 ± 2.99	91.62 ± 0.99	6/5	92.38 ± 6.07
3g	79.42 ± 2.06	85.95 ± 3.13	5/5	85.00 ± 6.94
3h	5.40 ± 1.39	5.20 ± 1.56	5/5	73.78 ± 1.83
3i	6.78 ± 1.67	3.43 ± 1.33	5/5	95.25 ± 1.91
3j	34.90 ± 4.80	66.63 ± 3.90	5/4	384.90 ± 3.40
3k	49.80 ± 3.27	62.14 ± 3.44	5/4	97.68 ± 11.78
3l	47.96 ± 5.18	49.67 ± 4.47	4/4	719.95 ± 31.35
3m	9.70 ± 2.41	9.49 ± 2.17	5/5	121.50 ± 7.30
3n	68.43 ± 4.84	75.00 ± 3.14	4/6	86.41 ± 3.18
3o	7.64 ± 0.84	5.22 ± 1.49	4/6	146.80 ± 5.05
6a	54.32 ± 3.11	68.93 ± 3.57	4/7	299.35 ± 41.25
6b	39.93 ± 4.78	59.85 ± 3.15	11/6	497.90 ± 3.90
6c	75.62 ± 2.36	76.05 ± 2.22	6/6	250.85 ± 0.45
6d	45.00 ± 3.55	57.18 ± 3.27	6/4	260.50 ± 3.80
6e	81.12 ± 2.62	79.19 ± 2.84	6/5	100.75 ± 1.96
6f	93.17 ± 1.11	91.77 ± 0.71	6/5	101.75 ± 9.27
6g	92.12 ± 1.48	92.37 ± 1.82	6/5	81.29 ± 9.35
6h	29.85 ± 2.73	58.40 ± 4.37	6/5	380.56 ± 16.35
6i	31.90 ± 4.16	57.65 ± 3.47	7/6	164.70 ± 13.50
6j	35.63 ± 1.09	60.00 ± 4.39	4/7	390.45 ± 19.05
6k	48.56 ± 2.99	85.53 ± 0.21	6/4	>900
6l	38.17 ± 3.80	48.78 ± 4.13	7/4	332.70 ± 7.60

^a Relative inhibition (RI) was calculated as the ratio of steady-state currents evoked by 1 mM L-glutamate in the presence and absence of a 3 μM of the tested compound (multiplied by 100) at a membrane potential of -60 mV. Further details are described in the text. Data are presented as mean ± SEM; n = number of measured HEK293 cells. For cytotoxicity data, n = 3.

Table 3

Concentration-dependent analysis of the inhibitory effect of 6f and 3l at human GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptors measured at different membrane potentials.

Compound	Receptors	IC ₅₀ (-60 mV) (μM)	h (-60 mV)	IC ₅₀ (40 mV) (μM)	h (40 mV)	n (-60/ 40 mV)
6f	hGluN1/ hGluN2A	0.36 ± 0.06	1.12 ± 0.11	22.37 ± 3.43	1.16 ± 0.07	4/7
	hGluN1/ hGluN2B	0.16 ± 0.01	1.00 ± 0.05	11.67 ± 1.23	1.01 ± 0.05	7/10
3l	hGluN1/ hGluN2A	4.42 ± 0.90	0.76 ± 0.02	276.46 ± 20.65	1.23 ± 0.07	4/5
	hGluN1/ hGluN2B	4.40 ± 0.42	0.92 ± 0.03	214.75 ± 12.60	1.07 ± 0.08	9/9
Mem	hGluN1/ hGluN2A	0.84 ± 0.07	0.91 ± 0.08	28.07 ± 1.80	0.78 ± 0.54	6/8
	hGluN1/ hGluN2B	0.78 ± 0.09	1.04 ± 0.03	25.63 ± 1.36	1.16 ± 0.04	5/7
Ket	hGluN1/ hGluN2A	0.50 ± 0.06	0.84 ± 0.04	53.32 ± 8.63	0.68 ± 0.05	8/4
	hGluN1/ hGluN2B	0.51 ± 0.05	1.01 ± 0.04	15.22 ± 0.60	0.87 ± 0.01	5/6

Experimental data obtained using a minimum of six concentrations of each compound were analyzed using Equation 1; IC₅₀ values (in μM), Hill coefficient values (h), and numbers of cells analyzed (n) are shown for both membrane potentials (-60 mV or 40 mV). Results are shown as mean ± SEM values (see Fig. 2). The values for memantine (Mem) and ketamine (Ket) were measured under identical experimental conditions in this study (Ketamine: hGluN1/hGluN2B) and were recently published [22,34].

voltage-dependent inhibitors with varying potencies at the studied NMDA receptors.

To determine the differences in the binding mode between MK-801 and compounds 3l and 6f, we carried out *in silico* analysis of the hGluN1/hGluN2A receptor [20]. The computational study involved initial molecular modeling with follow-up 10 ns molecular dynamic simulation. Results for the top-ranked binding poses of the ligands are illustrated in Fig. 3A–D. All the compounds bound into the vestibule of the ion channel, accommodating between the M3 helix-bundle crossing and the M2-pore loops, presumably blocking ion permeation. However, each ligand revealed a slightly different occupancy of the binding pocket. Compared to the previous study refining the spatial characteristics of MK-801 bound to hGluN1/hGluN2B receptor [18], our analysis revealed slightly different binding modes of the ligands (Fig. 3A). The comparison could be made based on the fact that the M3 helix-bundle crossings and the M2-pore loops are identical for both hGluN1/hGluN2A and hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors. Our analysis showed that MK-801 is more distanced from two pore-loop asparagine residues, N614 (hGluN2A) and N616 (hGluN1), thus being unable to form hydrogen contact with the secondary amine group of MK-801. Another difference can be observed for the methyl substituent of MK-801 that faced outside the L642 residue of the M3 helix of the hGluN2A subunit. Two aromatic rings of MK-801 were also oriented outside the V644 residue of the M3 helix of the hGluN1 subunit. In agreement with the crystallography of MK-801 to hGluN1/hGluN2B receptor, the side chains of N616 (hGluN1), N614 (hGluN2A), and N615 (hGluN2A) residues protruded out to the vestibule of the receptor, interacting with MK-801. Interestingly, compound 3l displayed favorable orientation in the receptor pore but differently than MK-801 (Fig. 3B). Firstly, the secondary amine of the ligand was near the amide backbone of F613 residue (hGluN2A). Notably, F613 residue (hGluN2A) was also involved in distorted π-π stacking with one of the benzene rings of 3l. The terminal hydroxyl group of the ligand imposed two hydrogen bond interactions with the amide of the N615 residue (hGluN2A) and the carbonyl oxygen of the L611 residue (hGluN2A). Likewise, 3l was adjacent to N-site asparagines, namely N616 (hGluN1), N614 (hGluN2A), and N615 (hGluN2A) residues, contributing significantly to the blocking properties of the compound. The occupancy pattern of 6f in the hGluN1/hGluN2A receptor differed from that of MK-801 and 3l (Fig. 3C). The compound revealed hydrophobic interactions with V644 (hGluN1) and L642 (hGluN2A) residues. The amine group of 6f formed a hydrogen bond interaction with N614 (hGluN2A). Also, other asparagine residues contributed to ligand anchoring, highlighting the adjacent N615 (hGluN1) and N615 (hGluN2A) residues. In summary, the *in silico* study revealed that the bulky pore vestibule can differently accommodate a vast array of amine-based ligands (Fig. 3D).

In the next phase, we aimed to examine the kinetics of inhibition induced by 6f and 3l at both NMDA receptor subtypes. Similar to our previous study [62], we determined the time constants of onset (τ_{on}) and offset (τ_{off}) of inhibition and induced by different concentrations of 6f (1, 10, 100 μM) and 3l (10, 100, 300 μM), measured in the steady-state conditions of the current responses induced by 1 mM L-glutamate and 100 μM glycine at a holding potential of -60 mV (Fig. 4A and B). Using one- or two-parameter exponential fits, we discovered that the compound 6f exhibited significantly slower τ_{off} values than those of the 3l compound at both NMDA receptor subtypes, although no significant differences were observed in τ_{on} values. (Fig. 4C and D). Comparison of the τ_{on} and τ_{off} values obtained for 10 μM of compounds 6f and 3l with previously reported values for 10 μM memantine and ketamine at hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors showed that the τ_{on} values were significantly slower for both 6f and 3l compared to memantine and ketamine, while only the τ_{off} value for 6f was markedly slower compared to the other compounds (Fig. 4E). Inhibitory effects of the 3l and 6f compounds was also compared with 1 μM dizocilpine (MK-801) at hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors (Fig. 4F). Using a similar approach as for 3l and 6f compounds, the analysis showed ~99 % relative inhibition, with

Fig. 2. Compound **6f** is a more potent voltage-dependent inhibitor of hGluN1/hGluN2A and hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors than compound **3l**. (A, C) Representative whole-cell voltage-clamp recordings of HEK293 cells expressing hGluN1/hGluN2A or hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors showing the inhibitory effects of compound **6f** (0.03–300 μ M) and compound **3l** (0.3–300 μ M) at membrane potentials of 40 mV (A) and –60 mV (C). Glu = 1 mM L-glutamate. (B, D) Normalized inhibitory concentration-response curves for compound **6f** and compound **3l** for hGluN1/hGluN2A and hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors at membrane potentials of 40 mV (B) and –60 mV (D). Concentration-response curves were fitted using Equation (1); the resulting IC_{50} values, Hill coefficients, and the numbers of cells measured for each membrane potential are shown in Table 3.

a τ_{on} value of 404.1 ± 44.0 ms ($n = 8$) (Fig. 4G). As mentioned, the irreversible nature of MK-801 limited our ability to measure the entire τ_{off} curve due to the constraints of electrophysiological recordings. Therefore, we analyzed the inhibition after a 2-min washout period, resulting in $\sim 56\%$ inhibition of the steady-state current amplitudes (Fig. 4G). This experiment demonstrated that the inhibitory kinetics of MK-801 at the hGluN1/hGluN2A receptor differ significantly from those of the **3l** and **6f** compounds. This indicates that the two compounds might exert distinct pharmacological effects *in vivo*. A relevant comparison can be made with MK-801, known for its potent psychomimetic properties attributed to its high affinity and nearly irreversible blockade of NMDA receptors [18,27].

Next, we analyzed the safety profile of the compounds on the eukaryotic cell line CHO-K1 using 3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide (MTT) (Table 2). IC_{50} values in the tens to thousands of μ M generally relate to the intermediate cytotoxicity of the tested compounds. Compounds **3l** and **6k** were identified as the least cytotoxic compounds with 720 and > 900 μ M values, respectively. Compound **3l** carries a hydrophilic ethanolamine moiety, which could ensure its low cell permeability and low cytotoxicity [63]. On the other hand, compound **6k** bears more lipophilic pyrrolidine moiety, lowering its solubility. Indeed, we could not determine the IC_{50} value due to its limited solubility in an aqueous solution, but the highest tested concentration (900 μ M) was insufficient to reduce cell viability to 50%, and other artifacts like plastic wall sticking should be considered.

Finally, we evaluated the ability to inhibit human cholinesterases (AChE and BuChE). Applied Ellman's method revealed only weak inhibitory activity in cyclohexylamine (**3g** and **6g**) ($IC_{50} = 14.4 \pm 1.3$

μ M, $IC_{50} = 8.5 \pm 0.4$ μ M respectively) and piperidine (**6h**) ($IC_{50} = 16.5 \pm 0.9$ μ M) derivatives on BuChE was found. The other compound showed no inhibitory activity on cholinesterases in tested concentrations (up to 100 μ M).

Based on our *in vitro* electrophysiological data, we selected compounds **3g**, **6g**, and **6f**, which showed high ($\sim 90\%$) relative inhibition at both NMDA receptor subtypes studied, for the next phase of *in vivo* investigation. We further selected compound **3l**, which exhibited moderate ($\sim 50\%$) inhibition at both NMDA receptor subtypes studied, due to the possibility that strong inhibitor potency to the NMDA receptor may lead to psychomimetic side effects *in vivo*. Compounds **3l** and **6f** with an aliphatic side chain also showed the lowest cytotoxic effect in the respective class of moderate to high potency compounds, which was not the case for compounds **3g** and **6g**, highly potent inhibitors of the NMDA receptors bearing a lipophilic cyclohexylamine moiety.

2.5. *In vivo* pharmacokinetic and toxicity study

The four selected compounds were first evaluated for their ability to cross the BBB, a key property of drugs targeting CNS disorders. A rat model was used for the pilot pharmacokinetic evaluation, and the compounds were evaluated at two time points, namely at 15 and 60 min after intraperitoneally (*i.p.*) administration of the 5 mg/kg dose (Fig. 5). The data obtained confirmed the ability of all the tested compounds to cross the BBB, although we observed slight differences between individual compounds. Specifically, the best brain penetration was observed for **3l**, while the other 3 compounds showed the same pattern and rapid elimination from the brain. Due to the higher cytotoxicity and lower

Fig. 3. Top-scored docking poses from *in silico* simulation. MK-801 (purple; **A**), **3l** (green; **B**), and **6f** (yellow; **C**). The spatial overlap of all the compounds under the *in silico* study is displayed in part **D**. The crucial amino acid residues from the transmembrane domain of the hGluN1/hGluN2A receptor (PDB ID: 7EU7) [20] are shown in blue, and orange, belonging to GluN1 and GluN2A subunits, respectively. Figures were created with The PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 2.4.1, Schrödinger, LLC.

solubility (data not shown) of compounds **3g** and **6g**, we decided to proceed further with compounds **3l** and **6f** as representatives of compounds with moderate (**3l**) or high (**6f**) potency for NMDA receptors, in the following behavioral and neuroprotective assays *in vivo*. However, before these studies, we assessed the no-observed-adverse-effect dose level (NOAEL). Both compounds **3l** and **6f** were safe at 10 mg/kg, whereas a decrease in respiration and activity loss was observed at 20 mg/kg. Therefore, the NOAEL was set as 10 mg/kg.

2.6. Evaluation of behavioral side effects of **3l** and **6f**

As noted above, an important limitation of the clinical use of NMDA receptor antagonists is their potential induction of severe psychotomimetic side effects, which in laboratory rodents manifest as hyperlocomotion, impaired prepulse inhibition of the startle response, and other behavioral changes [64–66]. Considering our *in vitro* data and ability to cross the BBB and NOAEL dose of 10 mg/kg, we next evaluated the effects of the compounds **3l** and **6f** at two doses, 1 and 10 mg/kg (administered *i.p.*) on locomotion in the open field test and on prepulse inhibition of startle response in rats. The prototypical high-affinity

“irreversible” open-channel blocker of the NMDA receptor, MK-801, was used as a comparator drug. First, analysis of the distance that laboratory rats moved in the open-field test for 10 min showed that 0.2 mg/kg MK-801 induced significant hyperlocomotion; in contrast, the tested compounds **3l** and **6f** did not affect the locomotor activity of the rats, at either the 1 or 10 mg/kg dose used (Fig. 6A). Interference of individual NMDA receptor antagonists with physiological neurotransmission and hence risk of their behavioral side effects varies, depending most probably on the mechanism of interaction with the receptor and pharmacological properties [66,67]. The observed undesirable hyperlocomotion-inducing effects of MK-801 follow the published literature [64,66,68,69]. Some other open-channel blockers of the NMDA receptors, phencyclidine (10 mg/kg) and ketamine (100 mg/kg), also substantially increased locomotor activity [66]. Even the memantine (30 mg/kg) increased locomotion, although its effect was milder when compared to the aforementioned blockers [66]. The more favorable side-effect profile of memantine was attributed to its faster blocking kinetics, stronger voltage dependency, and lower affinity compared with MK-801 [70,71]. In contrast, competitive antagonists of the NMDA receptors, such as CGP-37849, do not exhibit hyperlocomotion-inducing

Fig. 4. Derivative **6f** exhibits a markedly slower inhibition offset than **3l** at hGluN1/hGluN2A and hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors. (A, B) Representative whole-cell voltage-clamp recordings of HEK293 cells expressing hGluN1/hGluN2A or hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors showing inhibition onset and offset of 10 and 100 μM **6f** (A) and 100 and 300 μM **3l** (B) at a membrane potential of -60 mV. Glu = 1 mM L-glutamate. (C, D) Summary of calculated onset (τ_{on} ; G) and offset (τ_{off} ; H) time constants for **6f** and **3l** inhibition of hGluN1/hGluN2A or hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors obtained using Equation (2) ($***p < 0.001$, t -test, $n \geq 5$). (E) Comparison of the τ_{on} and τ_{off} values obtained for 10 μM of compounds **6f** and **3l** (shown in C and D) with previously reported values for 10 μM memantine (Mem) and ketamine (Ket) [22] ($***p < 0.001$, ANOVA, **6f** vs. Mem, Ket or as indicated by line **3l** vs. Mem, Ket). (F) The representative current response of the hGluN1/hGluN2A receptors was recorded from a HEK293 cell held at a membrane potential of -60 mV, activated by 1 mM L-glutamate (Glu) and exposed to 1 μM MK-801 as indicated. I₁ = control steady-state current amplitude, I₂ = current amplitude inhibited by MK-801 application, I₃ = current amplitude after 2 min washout of MK-801. (G) Bar graph summarizing the relative inhibition of the steady-state current responses by 1 μM MK-801 (1-I₂/I₁) and after 2 min washout of MK-801 (1-I₃/I₁) as indicated in F ($***p < 0.001$, t -test, $n = 8$).

effects [66]; unfortunately, their therapeutic and neuroprotective potential is considered low [67,72].

Similarly, as in the open field test, in the test of the prepulse inhibition of the acoustic startle response, we observed that 0.3 mg/kg MK-801 induced a deficit in prepulse inhibition, whereas compounds **3l** and **6f** at 1 or 10 mg/kg did not impair prepulse inhibition (Fig. 6B). The observed impairing effect of MK-801 is consistent with the literature [65,73,74]. Regarding other compounds, phencyclidine (3–6 mg/kg) also impaired prepulse inhibition [73,75]; a similar effect was observed with ketamine (6 and 10 mg/kg) [76] and some competitive antagonists [73]. Memantine (20 mg/kg) was also proven to impair prepulse

inhibition in rats [77].

In conclusion, we did not detect undesirable psychotomimetic effects of **3l** and **6f** at significantly higher concentrations compared with MK-801, which showed marked psychotomimetic effects in agreement with the literature [64–66].

2.7. In vivo neuroprotective effect

Finally, we investigated whether the selected drugs exhibit neuroprotective effects in a model of hippocampal lesion induced by the application of 25 mM NMDA to the rat dorsal hippocampus, leading to

Fig. 5. The concentration of the selected compounds in plasma and brain at the 15 and 60-min intervals after 5 mg/kg *i.p.* in rats. Results are shown as mean \pm SEM ($n = 3$).

Fig. 6. The effects of **3l**, **6f** (1 and 10 mg/kg), and MK-801 on the locomotor activity of rats in the open field (A) and on the prepulse inhibition of startle response (PPI; B). The compounds **3l** and **6f** did not induce hyperlocomotion or deficit of the prepulse inhibition, indicating a low risk of psychotomimetic side effects. Conversely, MK-801 (0.2 mg/kg for open field and 0.3 mg/kg for PPI) disrupted both these parameters. * vs. vehicle (VEH), ** $p < 0.01$, **** $p < 0.0001$; ANOVA and Dunnett's multiple comparisons test, $F(5, 32) = 43.32$, $p < 0.0001$ for open field test, $F(5, 31) = 9.208$, $p < 0.0001$ for prepulse inhibition test.

excessive activation of NMDA receptors and subsequent extensive and long-lasting damage of CA1, CA3, gyrus dentatus and hilus in the affected hippocampus and surrounding neural tissue [78]. Our previous studies have demonstrated that this model is a suitable screening method to assess the potential neuroprotective effect of novel compounds acting at the NMDA receptors [79–81]. The total hippocampal damage score analysis revealed increased scores in NMDA-treated rats compared to control animals. Rats co-administered with NMDA and 30 μM **3l** showed significantly lower damage scores, whereas no significant neuroprotective effect was demonstrated in the case of **6f** (Fig. 7A and B). Importantly, our previous research demonstrated that memantine did not exhibit a neuroprotective effect under the same experimental conditions [79,80,82].

The efficacy of **3l** and inefficacy of **6f** in our neuroprotective assay is surprising, as **3l** shows approximately half the efficacy in inhibiting both NMDA receptor subtypes at a concentration of 3 μM (Table 2), and the IC_{50} value for hGluN1/hGluN2B receptors (which are associated with neurodegeneration [7] is approximately 27-fold higher (Table 3). The distribution to the brain (Fig. 5) is irrelevant here because both compounds were administered intrahippocampally. However, the high (30

μM) concentration may have erased the differences in inhibitory potency of **3l** and **6f**, as the dose is sufficient to elicit the desired neuroprotective effect. Indeed, we observed a (nonsignificant) dose-dependent trend toward hyperlocomotion in the open field (Fig. 6A), suggesting a higher activity of compound **3l**. This suggests that characteristics beyond chemical structure, such as the kinetics of inhibition at NMDA receptors, may play a crucial role in the clinical expression of the compounds' effects. Notably, both compounds exhibit similar τ_{on} values, but τ_{off} is significantly slower for **3l** compared to **6f**, making compound **3l** wash out faster (Fig. 4). This is corroborated by the irreversible nature of NMDA receptor inhibition by MK-801, which at the behavioral level results in more adverse effects compared to the NMDA receptor antagonist memantine, which has faster τ_{off} kinetics [18,22,26,61,66]. This is further supported by the fact that the activation of extrasynaptic, but not synaptic, NMDA receptors is associated with neurodegeneration [83]. In theory, open-channel blockers with different offset kinetics may distinctly block synaptic (phasic) over extrasynaptic (tonic) NMDA receptors, leading to different neuroprotective effects. In addition, affinity for other targets may also influence the manifestations of the compound. We have recently reported that the inhibitory effect of acetylcholinesterase (AChE) may be important and exacerbate the beneficial effect of compounds acting at NMDA receptors [81]. However, neither **3l** nor **6f** inhibited AChE or butyrylcholinesterase (BChE), suggesting they do not interfere with the cholinergic system. In addition, a recent study showed that structurally similar tricyclic annulen compounds, such as **3m**, exhibit antagonistic activity at the histamine H1 receptor [84], which could mediate additional *in vivo* effects; however, investigation of all potential off-targets is beyond the scope of this study focused on the NMDA receptors. Also, besides derivative **3m**, the authors in the article used compounds that contain a basic *N*-methyl group that is not directly attached to the tricyclic core. This is not the case with our compounds where, apart from molecules **3m** and **3o**, our derivatives have the amino group directly bound to the tricyclic core of the molecule. In conclusion, the studied compounds **3l** and **6f** at both doses showed a promising profile consistent with the low risk of adverse behavioral side effects typical of some other NMDA receptor antagonists.

3. Conclusion

Our primary goal was to discover novel compounds with high neuroprotective potential and low risk of psychotomimetic side effects. The rational design and subsequent electrophysiological testing of 27 novel dibenzo [*a,d*] [7]annulen derivatives demonstrated varying inhibitory activity toward the major NMDA receptor subtypes. Based on a

Fig. 7. The neuroprotective effect of **3I** and **6f** in the NMDA-induced model of hippocampal neurodegeneration. (A) Representative images of brain slices from rats administered the solutions containing 25 mM NMDA and vehicle (VEH), 30 μ M **3I** or **6f** into the dorsal hippocampus. (B) The total scores of the hippocampal damage for the indicated co-applications. * vs. PBS + VEH, * p < 0.05, *** p < 0.001, **** p < 0.0001; W (3.000, 13.14) = 76.62, p < 0.0001; Welch's ANOVA with Dunnett's T3 multiple comparisons test.

combination of *in silico* predictions, *in vitro* assays, and *in vivo* pharmacokinetics, we selected compounds **3I** and **6f** for further *in vivo* analysis based on their potency, bioavailability, and low cytotoxicity. Compound **6f** showed high inhibition of both GluN1/GluN2A and GluN1/GluN2B receptor subtypes, while compound **3I** showed moderate inhibition but exhibited significant neuroprotective effect in a model of NMDA-induced hippocampal neurodegeneration. Behavioral tests confirmed that both compounds **3I** and **6f** did not induce hyperlocomotion and prepulse inhibition deficits, suggesting a lower risk of psychomimetic side effects than other NMDA receptor antagonists, such as MK-801. Thus, compound **3I** became a prime candidate due to its neuroprotective effects and lower toxicity, suggesting its potential for therapeutic use with minimal adverse effects.

4. Experimental section

4.1. Chemistry

All chemical solvents and reagents were used in the highest available purity without further purification. They were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Prague, Czech Republic) or FluoroChem (Dublin, Ireland). The reactions were monitored by thin layer chromatography (TLC) on silica gel plates (60 F254, Merck, Prague, Czech Republic), and the spots were visualized by ultraviolet light (254 nm). Purification of crude products was carried out using columns of silica gel (silica gel 100, 0.063–0.200 mm, 70–230 mesh ASTM, Fluka, Prague, Czech Republic) and PuriFlash GEN5 column, 5.250 (Interchim, Montluçon, France; silica gel 100, 60 Å, 230–400 mesh ASTM, Sigma-Aldrich, Prague, Czech Republic). NMR spectra were recorded in deuterated chloroform (CDCl_3), deuterated methanol (CD_3OD), and deuterated dimethyl sulfoxide ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$) on Bruker Avance NEO 500 MHz spectrometer (499.87 MHz for ^1H NMR, and 125.71 MHz for ^{13}C NMR). Chemical shifts (δ) are reported in parts per million (ppm), and spin multiplicities are given as broad singlet (bs), doublet (d), doublet of doublet (dd), triplet (t), quartet (q), pentet (p), or multiplet (m). Coupling constants (J) are reported in Hz. Melting points were measured using an automated melting point recorder M – 565 (Büchi, Switzerland) and are uncalibrated. Gradient LC analysis (described below) confirmed >95 % purity for all the final compounds. High-resolution mass spectra (HRMS) and LC-UV purity of synthesized compounds were obtained by high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) with the mass

spectrometry (MS) gradient method. The system used in this study was Dionex Ultimate 3000 UHPLC: RS LPG quaternary Pump, RS Column Compartment, RS Autosampler, Diode Array Detector, Chromeleon (version 7.2.9 build 11323) software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) with Q Exactive Plus Orbitrap mass spectrometer with Thermo Xcalibur (version 4.3.73.11.) software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Detection was performed by mass spectrometry in positive mode. Settings of heated electrospray source were: Spray voltage 3.5 kV, Capillary temperature: 262 °C, Sheath gas: 50 arbitrary units, Auxiliary gas: 12.5 arbitrary units, Spare gas: 2.5 arbitrary units, Probe heater temperature: 300 °C, Max spray current: 100 μ A, S-lens RF Level: 50. Purity was determined by UV detection at a 254 nm wavelength. Kinetex EVO C18 (2.1 \times 50 mm, 1.7 μ m, Phenomenex, Torrance, California, USA) column was used. The mobile phase A was ultrapure water of ASTM I type (resistance 18.2 M Ω cm at 25 °C) prepared by Barnstead Smart2Pure 3 UV/UF apparatus (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) with 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid (LC-MS grade, VWR International, Radnor, PA, USA); mobile phase B was acetonitrile (MS grade, VWR International, Radnor, PA, USA) with 0.1 % (v/v) of formic acid. The flow was constant at 0.4 ml/min. The method started with 0.3 min of isocratic flow of 5 % B, then the gradient of B rose to 100 % B in 3 min and remained constant at 100 % B for 0.7 min. Then, the composition returned to 5 % B and equilibrated for 3.5 min. The total run time was 7.5 min. The column was tempered to 27 °C.

4.2. General procedure for the preparation of *N*-substituted-10,11-dihydro-5*H*-dibenzo [*a,d*] [7]annulene-5-amines (**3a-o**)

Primary or secondary amine (**2a-o**) (5.25 mM, 3.0 eq) (Scheme 1) was placed in a 50 mL flask and dissolved in 10 mL of dry MeCN. The reaction mixture was stirred under an argon atmosphere at room temperature. Commercially available 5-chloro-10,11-dihydro-5*H*-dibenzo [*a,d*] [7]annulene (**1**) (1.75 mM, 1.0 eq) was dissolved in 5 mL of dry MeCN and added dropwise to the reaction. The reaction was stirred for 3 h under an argon atmosphere at 40 °C. After cooling to room temperature, the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure, and the crude material was purified using flash chromatography (eluent $\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{MeOH}$ with 1 % of 25 % aq. NH_3 , gradient 98:2 \rightarrow 94:6) to obtain the final compounds as free bases. These were dissolved in 5 mL of MeOH and 1 mL of HCl (35 % aq. sol.) and were added dropwise at 0 °C. The reaction was maintained for 1 h at room temperature. The solvent was

evaporated under reduced pressure, and the residual water was removed by azeotropic distillation with absolute EtOH. The solid product was washed with acetone for the final hydrochloride salts (**3a-o**) as a yellowish solid.

4.2.1. *N-methyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (3a)*

Yield 17 %; white solid. M.p.: 238.9–240.6 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.54 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.42 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.37–7.31 (m, 4H), 5.43 (s, 1H), 3.52–3.41 (m, 2H), 3.14–3.02 (m, 2H), 2.63 (s, 3H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 140.31, 131.64, 131.07, 130.13, 126.74, 32.15, 31.21. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₆H₁₈N⁺ (*m/z*): 224.14337; found: 224.14308. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.2. *N-ethyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (3b)*

Yield 51 %; white solid. M.p.: 226.0–227.6 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.54 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.41 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.37–7.30 (m, 4H), 5.48 (s, 1H), 3.54–3.41 (m, 2H), 3.14–2.99 (m, 4H), 1.34 (t, *J* = 7.3 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 131.02, 130.05, 126.69, 42.00, 32.10, 10.02. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₇H₂₀N⁺ (*m/z*): 238.15902; found: 238.15881. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.3. *N-isopropyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (3c)*

Yield 52 %; white solid. M.p.: 202.2–203.9 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.56 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.42 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.36–7.30 (m, 4H), 5.56 (s, 1H), 3.51–3.40 (m, 2H), 3.34–3.31 (m, 1H), 3.14–3.02 (m, 2H), 1.40 (d, *J* = 6.6 Hz, 6H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 140.32, 132.23, 131.07, 130.04, 126.70, 50.09, 32.05, 18.13. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₈H₂₂N⁺ (*m/z*): 252.17467; found: 252.17441. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.4. *N-cyclopropyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (3d)*

Yield 62 %; white solid. M.p.: 204.6–205.6 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.59 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.42 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.37–7.30 (m, 4H), 5.61 (s, 1H), 3.55–3.42 (m, 2H), 3.14–3.01 (m, 2H), 2.64–2.56 (m, 1H), 0.96–0.91 (m, 2H), 0.88–0.82 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 129.14, 128.31, 124.90, 30.43, 28.01, 1.42. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₈H₂₀N⁺ (*m/z*): 250.15902; found: 250.15881. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.5. *N-butyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (3e)*

Yield 57 %; white solid. M.p.: 220.4–223.0 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.54 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.42 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.38–7.30 (m, 4H), 5.49 (s, 1H), 3.52–3.41 (m, 2H), 3.15–3.02 (m, 2H), 2.97–2.88 (m, 2H), 1.78–1.67 (m, 2H), 1.42–1.31 (m, 2H), 0.94 (t, *J* = 7.4 Hz, 3H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 131.02, 130.08, 126.70, 46.57, 32.10, 27.49, 19.57, 12.42. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₂₄N⁺ (*m/z*): 266.19032; found: 266.18967. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.6. *N-isobutyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (3f)*

Yield 24 %; white solid. M.p.: 195.6–196.2 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.54 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.42 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.37–7.30 (m, 4H), 5.52 (s, 1H), 3.51–3.40 (m, 2H), 3.18–3.04 (m, 2H), 2.81–2.72 (m, 2H), 2.17–2.05 (m, 1H), 1.00 (d, *J* = 6.7 Hz, 6H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 131.02, 130.11, 126.69, 53.92, 32.10, 25.40, 19.20. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₂₄N⁺ (*m/z*): 266.19032; found: 266.18994. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.7. *N-cyclohexyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (3g)*

Yield 19 %; white solid. M.p.: 218.4–220.3 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.55 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.41 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.37–7.29 (m, 4H), 5.61 (s, 1H), 3.51–3.40 (m, 2H), 3.15–3.02 (m, 2H), 3.00–2.90 (m, 1H), 2.26–2.17 (m, 2H), 1.90–1.81 (m, 2H), 1.72–1.64 (m, 1H), 1.52–1.37 (m, 2H), 1.31–1.14 (m, 3H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 140.35, 132.33, 131.04, 130.00, 126.68, 56.89, 32.07, 29.14, 24.55, 24.25. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₂₁H₂₆N⁺ (*m/z*): 292.20597; found: 292.20572. LC-MS purity 96 %.

4.2.8. *1-(10,11-Dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-yl)piperidine hydrochloride (3h)*

Yield 38 %; white solid. M.p.: 200.1–201.3 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.52 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.43 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.39–7.27 (m, 4H), 5.36 (s, 1H), 3.56–3.44 (m, 2H), 3.41–3.34 (m, 2H), 3.14–3.01 (m, 4H), 2.01–1.89 (m, 2H), 1.87–1.74 (m, 3H), 1.64–1.50 (m, 1H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 139.95, 132.86, 131.24, 130.73, 130.48, 126.51, 77.49, 52.63, 31.85, 22.52, 21.16. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₂₀H₂₄N⁺ (*m/z*): 278.19032; found: 278.19012. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.9. *4-(10,11-Dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-yl)morpholine hydrochloride (3i)*

Yield 60 %; white solid. M.p.: 185.6–187.2 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.53 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.44 (dt, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.41–7.28 (m, 4H), 5.44 (s, 1H), 4.10–3.95 (m, 2H), 3.91–3.77 (m, 2H), 3.62–3.48 (m, 2H), 3.32–3.19 (m, 4H), 3.16–2.99 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 140.23, 133.05, 131.31, 130.70, 129.91, 126.58, 78.60, 63.45, 51.73, 31.94. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₂₂NO⁺ (*m/z*): 280.16959; found: 280.16928. LC-MS purity 95 %.

4.2.10. *N-(2-methoxyethyl)-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (3j)*

Yield 56 %; white solid. M.p.: 205.8–207.2 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.53 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.41 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.36–7.30 (m, 4H), 5.57 (s, 1H), 3.63 (t, *J* = 5.1 Hz, 2H), 3.52–3.41 (m, 2H), 3.38 (s, 3H), 3.14 (t, *J* = 5.1 Hz, 2H), 3.12–3.04 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 131.02, 130.05, 126.68, 66.61, 57.81, 45.92, 32.07. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₈H₂₂NO⁺ (*m/z*): 268.16959; found: 268.16934. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.11. *1-(10,11-Dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-yl)pyrrolidine hydrochloride (3k)*

Yield 38 %; white solid. M.p.: 222.3–223.9 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.54 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.43 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.38–7.28 (m, 4H), 5.41 (s, 1H), 3.64–3.52 (m, 2H), 3.32–3.28 (m, 4H), 3.15–3.03 (m, 2H), 2.28–2.14 (m, 2H), 2.12–1.97 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 139.82, 132.12, 132.05, 131.24, 130.37, 126.63, 75.86, 54.00, 31.98, 22.18. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₂₂N⁺ (*m/z*): 264.17467; found: 264.17435. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.12. *2-((10,11-Dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-yl)amino) ethanol hydrochloride (3l)*

Yield 53 %; white solid. M.p.: 183.1–184.8 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.54 (dd, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.41 (td, *J* = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.36–7.30 (m, 4H), 5.60 (s, 1H), 3.84–3.78 (m, 2H), 3.54–3.43 (m, 2H), 3.15–3.02 (m, 4H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 131.02, 130.02, 126.67, 56.35, 32.11. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₇H₂₀NO⁺ (*m/z*): 254.15394; found: 254.15373. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.13. *1-(10,11-Dihydro-5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-yl)-4-methylpiperazine dihydrochloride (3m)*

Yield 33 %; white solid. M.p.: decomposition at 228.7 °C. ¹H NMR

(500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.26–7.19 (m, 4H), 7.17 (dd, J = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.12 (td, J = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 4.16 (s, 1H), 4.02–3.92 (m, 2H), 3.26–3.08 (m, 4H), 2.89–2.77 (m, 2H), 2.67–2.47 (m, 4H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 139.64, 137.79, 130.66, 130.61, 128.00, 125.50, 77.69, 53.71, 48.68, 42.06, 31.42. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_2^+$ (m/z): 293.20122; found: 293.20096. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.14. *N,N*-diethyl-10,11-dihydro-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (**3n**)

Yield 55 %; white solid. M.p.: 166.2–167.4 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 9.87 (s, 1H), 7.55 (dd, J = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.39 (td, J = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.30 (dd, J = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.27 (td, J = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 5.51 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 3.75–3.63 (m, 2H), 3.16–3.06 (m, 2H), 3.02–2.89 (m, 4H), 1.25 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO) δ 140.32, 132.94, 132.20, 131.77, 130.63, 126.78, 71.95, 44.32, 31.83, 8.10. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}^+$ (m/z): 226.19032; found: 266.19046. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.2.15. 1-(10,11-Dihydro-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-yl)-4-ethylpiperazine dihydrochloride (**3o**)

Yield 36 %; white solid. M.p.: decomposition at 239.3 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.26–7.19 (m, 4H), 7.16 (dd, J = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 7.11 (td, J = 7.5, 1.4 Hz, 2H), 4.14 (s, 1H), 4.04–3.90 (m, 2H), 3.24–2.96 (m, 6H), 2.89–2.75 (m, 2H), 2.67–2.42 (m, 4H), 1.28 (t, J = 7.3 Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 139.63, 137.94, 130.64, 130.60, 127.96, 125.48, 77.84, 51.64, 51.50, 48.81, 31.43, 8.47. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_2^+$ (m/z): 307.21687; found: 307.21658. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.3. General procedure for the preparation of *N*-substituted-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amines (**6a-l**)

Commercially available 5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-ol (**4**) (4.8 mM, 1.0 eq) was placed in 25 mL flask and dissolved in dry DCM, the flask was filled with argon and cooled to 0 °C. Solution of SOCl_2 (20.67 mM, 4.3 eq), 1 mL of dry DCM, and 1 drop of pyridine was added dropwise. The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 12 h under an argon atmosphere. After the reaction, the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure, and the crude material was crystallized from petroleum ether to obtain the compound (**5**) as a yellow solid. Compound **5** was used directly in the following reaction. Compounds **6a-l** were prepared according to the procedure used in 4.2.

4.3.1. *N*-methyl-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (**6a**)

Yield 43 %; white solid. M.p.: 208.7–209.7 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.75–7.69 (m, 2H), 7.66–7.60 (m, 2H), 7.60–7.54 (m, 4H), 7.25 (s, 2H), 5.66 (s, 1H), 2.36 (s, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 133.62, 130.91, 130.44, 130.35, 130.26, 129.54, 129.46, 68.17, 30.74. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for (m/z): 222.12772; found: 222.12752. LC-MS purity 98 %.

4.3.2. *N*-ethyl-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (**6b**)

Yield 44 %; white solid. M.p.: 189.0–190.9 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.76–7.71 (m, 2H), 7.64–7.60 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.53 (m, 4H), 7.25 (s, 2H), 5.76 (s, 1H), 2.70 (q, J = 7.3 Hz, 2H), 1.21 (t, J = 7.3 Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 133.83, 130.98, 130.44, 130.32, 130.20, 129.47, 129.43, 66.44, 41.31, 9.54. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}^+$ (m/z): 236.14337; found: 236.14259. LC-MS purity 99 %.

4.3.3. *N*-isopropyl-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (**6c**)

Yield 41 %; white solid. Melting point (m.p.): 189.5–190.7 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.80–7.74 (m, 2H), 7.64–7.59 (m, 2H), 7.58–7.51 (m, 4H), 7.27 (s, 2H), 5.87 (s, 1H), 2.95 (hept, J = 6.6 Hz,

1H), 1.21 (d, J = 6.6 Hz, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 133.97, 131.29, 130.58, 130.10, 129.98, 129.44, 129.36, 64.73, 50.03, 17.97. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}^+$ (m/z): 250.15902; found: 250.15836 94 %. LC-MS purity 95 %.

4.3.4. *N*-cyclopropyl-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (**6d**)

Yield 68 %; white solid. M.p.: 195.5–196.0 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.79–7.74 (m, 2H), 7.64–7.59 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.53 (m, 4H), 7.24 (s, 2H), 5.84 (s, 1H), 2.17–2.08 (m, 1H), 0.83–0.76 (m, 2H), 0.75–0.69 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 132.36, 129.43, 128.97, 128.87, 128.54, 127.90, 127.81, 66.85, 27.47, 1.42. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}^+$ (m/z): 248.14337; found: 248.14290. LC-MS purity 98 %.

4.3.5. *N*-butyl-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (**6e**)

Yield 57 %; white solid. M.p.: 202.7–203.2 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.76–7.71 (m, 2H), 7.65–7.60 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.53 (m, 4H), 7.26 (s, 2H), 5.77 (s, 1H), 2.65–2.56 (m, 2H), 1.64–1.53 (m, 2H), 1.31–1.18 (m, 2H), 0.87 (t, J = 7.4 Hz, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 133.81, 130.96, 130.45, 130.35, 130.20, 129.49, 129.44, 66.73, 45.85, 26.99, 19.46, 12.33. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}^+$ (m/z): 264.17467; found: 264.17410. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.3.6. *N*-isobutyl-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (**6f**)

Yield 42 %; white solid. M.p.: 183.6–184.4 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.77–7.72 (m, 2H), 7.65–7.61 (m, 2H), 7.60–7.54 (m, 4H), 7.28 (s, 2H), 5.79 (s, 1H), 2.45 (d, J = 7.1 Hz, 2H), 2.01–1.90 (m, 1H), 0.88 (d, J = 6.7 Hz, 6H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 133.71, 130.88, 130.52, 130.38, 130.17, 129.50, 66.78, 53.04, 24.81, 18.98. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}^+$ (m/z): 264.17467; found: 264.17392. LC-MS purity 99 %.

4.3.7. *N*-cyclohexyl-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (**6g**)

Yield 74 %; white solid. M.p.: 199.8–200.2 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.78–7.73 (m, 2H), 7.65–7.60 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.52 (m, 4H), 7.27 (s, 2H), 5.91 (s, 1H), 2.63–2.52 (m, 1H), 1.98–1.90 (m, 2H), 1.83–1.73 (m, 2H), 1.65–1.57 (m, 1H), 1.36–1.24 (m, 2H), 1.18–1.03 (m, 3H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 133.98, 131.24, 130.58, 130.11, 130.00, 129.43, 129.38, 64.60, 56.85, 28.94, 24.41, 24.24. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}^+$ (m/z): 290.19032; found: 290.18954. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.3.8. 1-(5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-yl)piperidine hydrochloride (**6h**)

Yield 44 %; white solid. M.p.: 169.8–171.0 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, DMSO- d_6) δ 8.52–8.40 (m, 1H), 7.86–7.81 (m, 2H), 7.69–7.64 (m, 2H), 7.60–7.53 (m, 4H), 6.26–6.15 (m, 1H), 2.78–2.61 (m, 4H), 1.86–1.73 (m, 2H), 1.70–1.58 (m, 2H), 1.56–1.36 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, DMSO) δ 134.55, 132.18, 131.15, 130.70, 130.13, 129.82, 51.28, 21.71, 20.74. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}^+$ (m/z): 276.17467; found: 276.17404. LC-MS purity 99 %.

4.3.9. 4-(5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-yl)morpholine hydrochloride (**6i**)

Yield 52 %; white solid. M.p.: 171.1–172.7 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol- d_4) δ 7.79–7.73 (m, 2H), 7.69–7.64 (m, 2H), 7.63–7.57 (m, 4H), 7.28 (s, 2H), 5.92 (s, 1H), 3.96–3.85 (m, 3H), 3.74–3.65 (m, 2H), 3.28–3.22 (m, 1H), 3.18–3.09 (m, 2H), 2.78–2.69 (m, 2H). ^{13}C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 134.14, 131.67, 130.48, 130.45, 130.05, 129.50, 128.77, 127.90, 76.97, 63.49, 62.42, 51.12, 43.26. HRMS (ESI $^+$): [M + H] $^+$: calculated for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{20}\text{NO}^+$ (m/z): 278.15394; found: 278.15356. LC-MS purity 97 %.

4.3.10. *N*-(2-methoxyethyl)-5H-dibenzo [*a,d*][7]annulen-5-amine hydrochloride (**6j**)

Yield 52 %; white solid. M.p.: 189.1–190.8 °C. ^1H NMR (500 MHz,

Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.74–7.71 (m, 2H), 7.64–7.61 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.53 (m, 4H), 7.27 (s, 2H), 5.81 (s, 1H), 3.52–3.46 (m, 2H), 3.32 (s, 3H), 2.90–2.81 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 133.67, 130.97, 130.48, 130.33, 130.18, 129.48, 66.81, 66.18, 57.75, 45.17. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₈H₂₀NO⁺ (*m/z*): 266.15394; found: 266.15411. LC-MS purity 99 %.

4.3.11. 1-(5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-yl)pyrrolidine hydrochloride (6k)

Yield 58 %; white solid. M.p.: 170.1–171.3 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.76–7.73 (m, 2H), 7.66–7.62 (m, 2H), 7.59–7.56 (m, 4H), 7.30 (s, 2H), 5.74 (s, 1H), 3.15–3.05 (m, 2H), 2.88–2.80 (m, 2H), 2.19–2.08 (m, 2H), 1.99–1.88 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 133.63, 131.06, 130.51, 130.50, 130.19, 129.67, 129.49, 74.64, 53.89, 22.66. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₉H₂₀N⁺ (*m/z*): 262.15902; found: 262.15942. LC-MS purity 99 %.

4.3.12. 2-((5H-dibenzo [a,d][7]annulen-5-yl)amino)ethanol hydrochloride (6l)

Yield 69 %; white solid. M.p.: 181.5–182.3 °C. ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Methanol-*d*₄) δ 7.75–7.70 (m, 2H), 7.66–7.61 (m, 2H), 7.60–7.53 (m, 4H), 7.28 (s, 2H), 5.85 (s, 1H), 3.69–3.63 (m, 2H), 2.80–2.73 (m, 2H). ¹³C NMR (126 MHz, MeOD) δ 133.62, 131.03, 130.49, 130.29, 130.20, 129.51, 129.47, 66.60, 55.92. HRMS (ESI⁺): [M + H]⁺: calculated for C₁₇H₁₈NO⁺ (*m/z*): 252.13829; found: 252.13858. LC-MS purity 99.9 %.

4.4. Molecular biology and preparation of transfected HEK293 cells

We used cDNA vectors for expression in mammalian cells carrying genes for the human versions of the GluN1-1a (hGluN1), GluN2A (hGluN2A), and GluN2B (hGluN2B) subunits [85]. HEK293 cells were cultured in 24-well plates in Opti-MEM I medium containing 5 % fetal bovine serum (FBS; all from Thermo Fischer Scientific, Prague, Czech Republic). Confluent HEK293 cells were transfected using a mixture of 50 μ l of Opti-MEM I containing a total of 0.9 μ g of cDNA constructs encoding hGluN1/hGluN2 subunits and GFP (for identification of successfully transfected cells; pQBI 25, Takara) in a 1:1:1 ratio, plus 0.9 μ l of PolyMag Transfection Reagent (OZ BIOSCIENCES, Marseille, France). After a 20 min incubation on a magnetic plate, HEK293 cells were trypsinized and cultured on 3 cm diameter poly-L-lysine-coated coverslips in Opti-MEM I medium containing 1 % FBS, 20 mM MgCl₂ and 3 mM kynurenic acid (to prevent cell death caused by excitotoxic NMDA receptor activation) [62].

4.5. In silico calculation

Molecular docking was used for binding pose calculations. The 3D structures of MK-801, **3l**, and **6f** were built by OpenBabel, v. 2.3.215, and optimized by Avogadro, v. 1.2.0, using the force fields GAFF [86]. The ligands were converted into pdbqt-format by OpenBabel, v. 2.3.2. The hGluN1/hGluN2A structure was gained from the RCSB database (PDB ID: 7EU7, resolution 3.5 Å) [20] and prepared for docking by the function DockPrep of the software Chimera, v. 1.14 [87]. and by MGLTools, v. 1.5.4 [88]. The docking calculations were made by Vina, v. 1.1.2, as semi-flexible with flexible ligands and rigid receptors [89]. The docking pose of ligands was then improved by molecular dynamic (MD) simulation. The receptor structure was prepared using the software Chimera. The best-scored docking poses were taken as the starting point for MD. The force-field parameters for ligands were assessed by Antechamber, v. 20.0 [90] using General Amber force-field 2 [91]. MD simulation was carried out by Gromacs, v. 2018.1 [92]. The complex receptor-ligand was solvated in the periodic water box using the TIP3P model. The system was neutralized by adding Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions to a concentration of 100 mM. The system energy was minimized and equilibrated in a 100-ps isothermal-isochoric NVT and then a 100-ps isothermal-isobaric NPT phase. Then, a 10 ns MD simulation was run

at a temperature of 300 K. The molecular docking and MD results were 3D visualized by the PyMOL Molecular Graphics System, Version 2.4.1, Schrödinger, LLC. The Supporting Information contains data for calculated ligand-receptor complexes, evaluated using Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD; Fig. S1), Root Mean Square Fluctuation (RMSF; Fig. S2) analyses, and binding energies (Table S3).

4.6. Electrophysiology

Patch-clamp measurements in the whole-cell configuration were performed 16–48 h after the end of transfection using an Axopatch 200B amplifier (Molecular Devices, California, USA); cell current responses were low-pass filtered at 2 kHz using a 4-pole Bessel low-pass filter, digitized at 5 kHz, and recorded using Clampex 10 software (Axon Instruments, Molecular Devices). The series resistance and capacitance of all measured cells were monitored and compensated to 80 % [62]. Glass micropipettes with a tip resistance of 3–6 M Ω were prepared using a micropipette puller model P-1000 (Sutter Instrument Co., California, USA) and were filled with an intracellular solution containing (in mM): 125 gluconic acid, 15 CsCl, 10 BAPTA 10 HEPES, 3 MgCl₂, 0.5 CaCl₂ and 2 ATP-Mg salts (pH 7.2 with CsOH). The extracellular recording solution (ECS) contained (in mM) 160 NaCl, 2.5 KCl, 10 HEPES, 10 D-glucose, 0.01 EDTA, and 1 CaCl₂ (pH 7.3 with NaOH). All chemicals were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Prague, Czech Republic). ECS exchange was performed using a rapid application system with a solution exchange time constant per cell of approximately 20 ms. All ECS contained a saturating concentration of the co-agonist – glycine (100 μ M), and NMDA receptor responses were induced by applying a saturating concentration of the agonist – L-glutamate (1 mM). The test compounds were dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at a concentration of 30 mM; all ECS used in a given experiment contained the same concentration of DMSO (\leq 1 %). Concentration-response inhibition curves were obtained using the

$$I = 1 / (1 + ([\text{compound}] / IC_{50})^h) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

where IC₅₀ is the concentration of the compound that caused 50 % inhibition of the L-glutamate-induced current, [compound] is the concentration of the tested compound, and h is the Hill coefficient [79].

The time course of inhibition by **6f** or **3l** was analyzed using a single or double exponential function, and the weighted time constants (τ_w) were obtained using the

$$\tau_w = (\tau_{\text{fast}} * A_{\text{fast}} + \tau_{\text{slow}} * A_{\text{slow}}) / (A_{\text{fast}} + A_{\text{slow}}) \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

where τ_{fast} and A_{fast} are the time constant and area of the faster component, and τ_{slow} and A_{slow} are the time constant and area of the slower component.

4.7. Cell viability assay

Standard MTT assay (Merck) was used according to the manufacturer's protocol on the CHO-K1 cell line (Chinese hamster ovary) to compare the cytotoxic effect of the studied compounds [93]. The CHO-K1 cells were cultured according to ECACC-recommended conditions and seeded in a density of 8000 cells per well. Briefly, the tested compounds were dissolved in DMSO and subsequently diluted in a growth medium (F-12) supplemented with 10 % FBS and 1 % penicillin/streptomycin so that the final concentration of DMSO did not exceed 0.5 % (v/v). The CHO-K1 cells were exposed to the tested compounds for 24 h. The medium was then replaced with medium containing 10 μ M MTT, and the cells were allowed to produce formazan for another approximately 3 h under surveillance. Thereafter, the medium with MTT was removed, and the formazan crystals were dissolved in DMSO (100 μ L). Cell viability was assessed spectrophotometrically by the amount of formazan produced. Absorbance was measured at a wavelength of 570 nm with a reference wavelength of 650 nm on

Synergy HT (BioTek, Winooski, USA). The IC₅₀ values were then calculated from the control-subtracted triplicates using non-linear regression (four parameters) in GraphPad Prism 5 software (GraphPad Software, San Diego, USA). The final IC₅₀ values were obtained as a mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM) from three independent measurements.

4.8. In vitro anti-cholinesterase assay

The inhibitory activity of novel compounds against human recombinant AChE (hAChE, E.C. 3.1.1.7, purchased from Merck) and human plasmatic butyrylcholinesterase (hBChE, E.C. 3.1.1.8, purchased from Merck) were determined using the modified Ellman's method, according to the previously published protocol with the highest concentration tested 100 μM [94]. The results are expressed as IC₅₀ values (the compound concentration required to reduce cholinesterase activity by 50 %). For the calculation of the degree of inhibition (I), the following was used:

$$I = \left(1 - \frac{\Delta A_i}{\Delta A_0}\right) \times 100 [\%] \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

where ΔA_i indicates the change in absorbance observed for adequate cholinesterase exposed to its corresponding inhibitor, and ΔA₀ indicates the change in absorbance when a phosphate buffer solution (PBS) was added instead of an inhibitor. Microsoft Excel 10 software (Microsoft Corporation, Redmont, USA) and Prism v. 5.02 (GraphPad Software, San Diego, USA) were used to evaluate the obtained data statistically.

4.9. In vivo pharmacokinetic study

4.9.1. Animals

Adult male Wistar rats (200–300 g) purchased from the Velaz breeding colony (Czech Republic) were used for the pharmacokinetic assessment of four selected compounds (**3g**, **3l**, **6f**, and **6g**). The experiments were conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the European Union directive 2010/63/EU and Act No. 246/1992 Coll. The experimental animals were handled under the supervision of the Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Military Health Sciences, Czech Republic (approvals reference No. 15/21 and 19/21).

The rats were injected intraperitoneally (*i.p.*) with the tested compounds (5 mg/kg in 5 % DMSO/5 % kolliphor/saline (v/v) mixture). Blood samples were collected under deep terminal anesthesia directly by cardiac puncture into heparinized 1.5 mL tubes at 15 and 60 min (three animals per time interval). Four animals were used for zero time or blank control. The animals were perfused transcardially with a saline solution (0.9 % NaCl) for 5 min (1 mL/min), and after the wash-out, the skull was opened and the brain carefully removed; brains were stored at –80 °C until homogenization. The brains were weighed, and PBS was added four times. Subsequently, the brains were homogenized by a T-25 Ultra Turrax disperser (IKA, Staufen, Germany), ultrasonicated by a UP 50H needle homogenizer (Hielscher, Teltow, Germany), and stored at –80 °C before extraction.

4.9.2. Sample extraction

190 μL of brain homogenate or plasma were spiked with 10 μL of internal standard (IS) isotope-labeled donepezil-d₇ in methanol (IS, final concentration was 1 μM). The sample was alkalized with 100 μL of 1 M sodium hydroxide, and 0.7 mL of *tert*-butyl methyl ether was added. The samples were then shaken (1200 RPM, 10 min, Wizard Advanced IR Vortex Mixer, Velp Scientifica, Usmate, Italy) and centrifuged (12,000 RPM, 5 min, Universal 320 R centrifuge, Hettich, Tuttingen, Germany). 500 μL of supernatant was transferred to a microtube and evaporated to dryness in a CentriVap concentrator (Labconco Corporation, Kansas City, USA). Calibration samples were prepared by the spiking of 180 μL of blank brain homogenate or plasma with 10 μL of the studied

compound dissolved in methanol (final concentrations range from 0.5 nM to 50 μM) and with 10 μL of IS, with a final concentration of 1 μM). The calibration samples were then vortexed and extracted as above. The analyzed samples were reconstituted in 100 μL of acetonitrile/water mixture of 50/50 (v/v).

4.9.3. Pharmacokinetic study - HPLC-MS analysis

Compound levels in plasma and brain homogenate were measured by the above-mentioned UHPLC system with mass spectrometric detection. The results were obtained by the gradient elution method with a reverse phase on an RP Amide column (Ascentis Express, 2.1 × 100 mm, 2.7 μm, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany). Mobile phase A was ultrapure water of ASTM I type (resistance 18.2 MΩ cm at 25 °C) prepared by Barnstead Smart2Pure 3 UV/UF apparatus (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Bremen, Germany) with 0.1 % (v/v) formic acid (LC-MS grade, Sigma-Aldrich, Steinheim, Germany); mobile phase B was acetonitrile (MS grade, VWR International, Fontenay-sous-Bois, France) with 0.1 % (v/v) of formic acid. The gradient was as follows. Initially, 10 % of mobile phase B flowed for 0.3 min; the gradient of mobile phase B then increased to 60 % during 2.7 min and then rose to 100 % in 0.7 min. After this 0.7 min of 100 % B flow, the composition returned to 10 % B and was equilibrated for 3.5 min. The total run time of the gradient elution method was 7.5 min. The rate of flow of the mobile phase was set to 0.45 mL/min, and the column was tempered to 40 °C. The injection volume was 5 μL. Samples were analyzed using the previously mentioned Orbitrap mass spectrometer in total ion current in positive mode. The calibration curves had 11 points, and concentrations ranged from 0.5 nM to 50 μM; curves in both cases were linear within the measured range [81].

4.10. Acute toxicity evaluation-NOAEL

The acute toxicities of the compounds were assessed at a non-observed-adverse-effect level (NOAEL). Compounds were administered intraperitoneally (*i.p.*, 5 % DMSO with 5 % Kolliphor in saline) in adult male Wistar rats. Rats were randomly assigned to the experimental groups consisting of four males per one administered dose of tested compounds. Selected doses were administered to identify NOEL and NOAEL with starting dose levels based on their solubility or according to our previous experience. All tested compounds were administered via *i.p.* injection in a standardized volume of 1 mL.kg⁻¹.

Treated rats were extensively observed for signs of toxicity in the first hour and then periodically for two days. Clinical signs such as cardiovascular, respiratory, and nervous system disability, weight loss, or reduction of food consumption were observed according to Laboratory Animal Science Association (UK) guidelines. The severity of symptoms was classified as mild, moderate, and substantial [95]. During all acute toxicity studies, we followed the rules: i) if a category of substantial severity was achieved, the animal was immediately euthanized by CO₂, and a lower/more appropriate dose was selected to continue the study; ii) if a severe adverse effect or death occurred within a few minutes after administration to the first animal in the group, the other animal was not treated, and a lower dose was selected as well; iii) in the case of mortality or surviving 48 h, all animals were euthanized by CO₂ and subjected to basic macroscopic necropsy [96].

4.11. Evaluation of behavioral side effects of **3l** and **6f**

4.11.1. Animals

Adult male Wistar rats (280–375 g, 2–3 months old) purchased from the Velaz breeding colony were used. The rats were housed in pairs in standard plexiglass boxes (42 × 21 × 20 cm) in the animal facility of the National Institute of Mental Health, Czech Republic, with a 12:12 h light/dark cycle and defined temperature and humidity. Water and food were available *ad libitum*. All experiments were conducted in the light phase of the day after a week-long acclimatization period. Before the

experiments, the animals were habituated to manipulation by the experimenter by handling. The experiments were performed in accordance with the guidelines of European Union directive 2010/63/EU and Act No. 246/1992 Coll. on the protection of animals against cruelty and were approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee of the National Institute of Mental Health (reference number MZDR 9928/2023-5/OVZ).

4.11.2. Treatment and experimental design

The compounds **31** and **6f** were administered at 1 and 10 mg/kg body weight doses 15 min before the experiment. MK-801 (+)-MK-801 hydrogen maleate, Sigma-Aldrich) was administered at the dose of 0.2 mg/kg body weight (open field test) and 0.3 mg/kg body weight (prepulse inhibition test) 30 min before the experiment. All compounds were first dissolved in DMSO (5 % of total vehicle volume; Dimethylsulfoxid Rotipuran® p.a., Carl Roth, Germany), and then a solution consisting of 5 % Kolliphor EL (Glentham Life Sciences, UK) in physiological saline was added. Control animals received vehicle (5 % DMSO in 5 % Kolliphor EL in saline) 15 min before the experiment. All drugs were administered intraperitoneally (*i.p.*). Injection volume was 1 ml/kg. The animals were pseudo-randomly assigned to six treatment groups: VEH (vehicle), MK-801, **31** (1), **31** (10), **6f** (1), and **6f** (10); the numbers in the brackets denote the doses used (1 or 10 mg/kg body weight). We used 8 animals in the VEH group and 6 animals in each group. Each animal underwent an open field test and then, after 3–4 days, a prepulse inhibition test with the same treatment.

4.11.3. Open field test

The apparatus consisted of a square arena (80 × 80 × 40 cm) made of black plastic, located in a separate room with defined light conditions. The animal was placed in the center of the apparatus and allowed to move freely for 10 min. The animal was recorded by a camera above the arena, connected to tracking software (EthoVision XT 16, Noldus, Netherlands). The arena was cleaned thoroughly between animals. The dependent variable was the distance moved by the animal [81].

4.11.4. Prepulse inhibition of acoustic startle response

The startle response is a reflex response to a sudden, intense stimulus. The prepulse inhibition of startle response is a measure of sensorimotor gating and refers to the physiological reduction of the amplitude of the startle response caused by the presentation of a weak stimulus (prepulse) immediately before the startle-inducing stimulus (pulse). During the prepulse inhibition test, acoustic stimuli are presented, and the motor startle responses of the rats are analyzed. The dependent variable is the percent of prepulse inhibition. The experiment was performed as described (the only difference being the time interval between the compound administration and the testing session) [79].

4.12. Evaluation of the neuroprotective effect of **31** and **6f**

4.12.1. Animals

Experiments were conducted in accordance with the guidelines of the European Union directive 2010/63/EU and approved by the Animal Care and Use Committee, which possesses the National Institutes of Health Statement of Compliance with Standards for Humane Care and Use of Laboratory Animals. Adult male Wistar rats (350–500 g) were used for experiments to assess the neuroprotective activity of compounds **31** and **6f**. The rats were kept in a controlled environment described above.

4.12.2. Compounds and experimental groups (treatment)

NMDA was dissolved in 10 mM sterile PBS to achieve a final concentration of 25 mM. Compounds were diluted in a vehicle consisting of sterile 0.9 % physiological saline solution containing 5 % DMSO (Merck Millipore) and 5 % Kolliphor EL to achieve a final concentration of 30 μM. The solutions containing NMDA at 25 mM and compound **31** of **6f** at

30 μM were thoroughly mixed in a 1:1 ratio. The control group of animals received a mixed solution of NMDA (25 mM) and vehicle. The second control group received a mixed solution of 10 mM PBS and vehicle. A total of $n = 37$ animals were used for the experiment ascribed to the following treatment groups: (1) PBS + VEH (received PBS and vehicle; $n = 9$); (2) NMDA + VEH (received NMDA and vehicle; $n = 7$); (3) NMDA + **31** (received NMDA and compound **31**; $n = 12$) and (4) NMDA + **6f** (received NMDA and compound **6f**; $n = 9$).

4.12.3. NMDA lesion and histology

The animals underwent surgical preparation under 1.5–2.5 % of isoflurane anesthesia (VetPharma). They were secured onto a stereotaxic apparatus (TSE systems, Berlin, Germany), with their eyes covered with a medical petroleum jelly (Vaseline, Unilever). They were carefully shaved, and the scalp was incised. A unilateral craniotomy was performed at the coordinates of - 4 mm AP and 2.5 mm ML relative to the bregma [97]. The right dorsal hippocampus was injected using a Hamilton 10 μL syringe (DV = 4.6 mm). An infusion pump (model 540310 plus, TSE Systems, Berlin, Germany) maintained a constant flow rate of 0.25 μL/min to apply the mixed solutions. The total volume administered to each animal was 2 μL. After surgery, the animals had free access to food and water containing analgesics. At 24 h after the application of the mixed NMDA and compounds **31** or **6f** solutions, the rats were euthanized with an overdose of the anesthetics Narketan (ketamine; 100 mg/kg) and Rometar (xylazine; 20 mg/kg). Transcranial perfusion was performed with 4 % paraformaldehyde (PFA) diluted in 0.2 M phosphate buffer (PB). Brains were post-fixed 24 h in 4 % PFA and gradually cryoprotected using increasing concentrations of sucrose solution (10, 20, and 30 %; the brain was immersed in the solution until it sank to the bottom of the tube). Frozen cryoprotected brains were sliced in the coronal plane (50 μm, 1-in-5 series) from the beginning of the hippocampus (Bregma - 1.80 mm). All sections were collected and stored at -20 °C in cryoprotectant solution (ethylene glycol, glycerol, 0.2 M PB, distilled water - 3:3:1:3). Each series of slices underwent evaluation of the neurodegenerative damage of the hippocampus. The severity of hippocampal damage was determined in the following hippocampal regions: granular cell layer of the lower part of the dentate gyrus (DGL), granular cell layer of the higher part of the dentate gyrus (DGH), hilus, CA1, and CA3, as previously described [98].

4.13. Statistics

Electrophysiological data are presented as mean ± standard error of the mean (SEM), and group differences were analyzed by *t*-test or ANOVA followed by Student-Newman-Keuls Method using SigmaStat 3.5 (Systat Software Inc.). Differences with a *p*-value <0.05 were considered statistically significant. The behavioral data were analyzed in GraphPad Prism 8 (San Diego, USA) using ANOVA with Dunnett's multiple comparisons test (vs. VEH group) and presented as mean + SEM. *p*-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant. In the data from prepulse inhibition, one outlier in the **6f** (10) group was removed (Grubbs test). The data concerning the neuroprotective effect of the compounds were also analyzed in GraphPad Prism 8 (San Diego, USA) and presented as mean + SEM; *p* < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. These data were assessed for normality (Shapiro-Wilk test) and homogeneity of variances (Brown-Forsythe test). As these data did not meet the assumption of homogeneity of variances, Welch's ANOVA was employed, followed by Dunnett's T3 multiple comparisons test.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jan Konecny: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Anna Misiachna:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marketa Chvojikova:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Lenka Kle-teckova:** Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Marharyta**

Kolcheva: Methodology, Investigation. **Martin Novak:** Methodology, Investigation. **Lukas Prchal:** Methodology, Investigation. **Marek Ladislav:** Methodology, Data curation. **Katarina Hemelikova:** Methodology. **Jakub Netolicky:** Investigation. **Martina Hrabanova:** Investigation, Methodology. **Tereza Koblrova:** Investigation, Data curation. **Jana Zdarova Karasova:** Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Jaroslav Pejchal:** Investigation, Data curation. **Jakub Fibigar:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology. **Zbynek Vecera:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology. **Tomas Kucera:** Data curation, Investigation, Methodology. **Pavla Jendelova:** Writing – original draft, Conceptualization. **Petra Zahumenska:** Data curation, Investigation. **Emily Langore:** Data curation, Investigation. **Jovana Doderovic:** Data curation, Investigation. **Yuan-Ping Pang:** Conceptualization. **Karel Vales:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Jan Korabecny:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Ondrej Soukup:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Martin Horak:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2024.116981>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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